

New Age Women and Work-Life Integration

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Logeswari.R., "New Age Women and Work-Life Integration." *Shanlax Internatioal Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 215–19.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586431>

Abstract

In the past, women have been inferior to men. Whether it comes to management positions, values, community norms, women have been trained that men are the greater gender and to stay in "HER's place". Things have changed a lot legally, but there are still these implicit norms given to women. In this era, women are proud of their personal, their careers, and their dreams. Women all around the world are placing themselves in ways that world have never seen before, representing them as New Age Women. But still these New Age Women are forced to drop their career or job due to unavoidable circumstances. 100 working women's feedback are pooled together for this study. The research article is formulated to chalk out that work and life of New Age Women is inseparable. The researcher contributes a suggestion based on the investigation.

Keywords: New Age Women, Work-Life Balance and Work-Life Integration.

Who are called New Age Women?

A new age woman is one who fights next to the inequity women face in the place of work. In other words, the New Age Woman is breach all the stereotypes and creating new limits. A beautiful word from the best tennis players the world has witnessed, Sania Mirza, New age woman, someone who never hesitates to speak what's on her mind and one of the best.

An article from Times of India 7th, March 2009, exactly one decade drafted a report on the title "The new age woman is here to stay!" (1). Gone are the days when a woman was supposed to play her part for others. Today, she matters to herself the most. She is ready to assert her own right and be what she aspires to be says Puja Bed.

The New Age Woman cannot only handle herself professionally but can sustain a strong household at the same time. She values education and knows how to have a balanced life. A working woman or a common woman of the modern era has no with holdings to live with various pressures of society. The New Age Woman is unconventional from the notion of marriage, and homemaking given her desires and voice are heard as the foremost main concern.

Research Problem

This article is written to square down the current scenario of working women who are obliged to be New Age Women's major problem is to separate work and life.

Research Questions

1. Who are new age women?
2. Which is more prior to them work or life?
3. Can New Age Women separate work and life?

Research Objectives

1. To identify the attributes of New Age Women.
2. To analysis the more prior attribute.
3. To identify the acceptance towards Work-life Integration.

Trending Transformation on Women Workforce

Annette Dixon, World Bank South Asia Vice President, at The Economic Times Women's Forum, Mumbai, on march 16th 2018 (2) delivered a speech stating that India ranks 120 among 131 countries in female labor force participation rates and rates of gender-based violence remain unacceptably high. In 2012, only 27 percent of adult Indian women had a job, or were actively looking for one, compared to 79 percent of men. In fact, almost 20 million women had dropped out of the work between 2005 and 2012.

In 2018, an article was published by Live Mint at Bangalore on a vibrant topic “ What prevents women in working?. The new encircling of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) conducted in 2015-16 shows that the proportion of working women has witnessed a sharp turn down compared to a decade ago. In 2005-06, when the last NFHS survey was conducted, 43% of married women in the age group of 15-49 years had reported working in the past 12 months. This quantity has declined to 31% in the latest survey. 98% of married men in the same age bracket reported having worked in the last 12 months, the data shows. Research shows that even women who have finished skill based courses and get jobs even tend to plunge out in response to family pressures. Changing social norms around marriage, work and household duties will have to be part of the agenda.

The dimension which is been considered for this research are Image Oriented, Career oriented, Family Oriented, work and life balance and work life integration.

Image Oriented

New Age Women believes in having a striking outer look both personally and professionally. The New Age Woman, living with a positive viewpoint gives her wisdom of delight and a good self-worth. More prominently, New Age Women is conscious of keeping a steadiness between just being called as purely a beautiful woman or a woman of center. If it is the final one, she is smart and admirable.

Career Oriented

The New Age Woman has a career to live for and a life full of thoughts and dreams. She is daring and knows how to be valued for her boundaries at work. She is good enough, positive, and equally artistic to her counter gender, men. She makes her environment and work-life exciting with her affirmative approach. Whatever she gets at hand finishes it with full willpower and dedication. If this she is filled up with, she is unquestionably a woman who values her work.

Family Oriented

The New Age women will not just have immense careers but can make and cultivate a beautiful family as well. The New Age Woman is the salvation of her family and knows how to maintain it mutually with her care, patience, and sacrifices. Her family is her main concern over quite a few other vital things that sprint down her brain.

Work-life balance

Work-life balance is the act of having an optimistic steadiness between one's private and professional life. In this challenging and demanding era it is very complicated for women to uphold the balance between the two as stress have increased leading to work pressure. Women have to make hard-hitting choices to reach this balance.

The ever shifting hassle of customer requirements and the job related responsibilities unswervingly influence the personal life of women employees making it difficult for them to fulfill the family responsibilities. On the other side of the coin, personal life can also be challenging if she is having kids or aging parents. Females in the workforce are now an important and enduring pressure group seeking for flexibility at work. Although both men and women divide work to fulfill their needs but still lumber is more on women shoulders with respect to family expectations, running home, taking care of children and parents. In our culture women thus face more challenges to thump stability between personal and professional life.

Review of Literature

Aggarwal (2012) indentified the association between work-life balance initiatives and employee's attitudes toward work-life disagreement and the place of work in general. Study recognized employees perceive work life balance enables them to work enhanced and suggested it should be a joint responsibility of Employer & Employee.

Goyal and Arora (2012) calculated the impact of work pressure on family life and the potential of family on the work commitments on 120 teachers of different educational institutes. The study revealed that factors like unconstructive attitude of family, family involvement, health related problems, long working durations, meetings, work consignment created an imbalance in their personal and professional lives.

Kumari, L. (2012) examined employees' insight about work life balance and it's relation with job satisfaction in Indian public sector banks. Study opened optimistic connection between the job satisfaction and work life balance and marks job satisfaction as a significant indicator of Work life balance.

Meenakshi and Ravichandran (2012) tinted problems faced by women teachers in gaining Work Life Balance and accordingly suggested ways which would advantage both individual and the institution. Study also stated that the women teachers knew the consequence of WLB and they tried to attain it by arranging their actions by appropriate time management.

Research Observation

An empirical study was conducted to find the remedy for the problem faced by New Age Women. Around 100 working women respondents were involved and contributed their feedback by answering the structured questionnaire.

In this study, content of the research is formulated with the dimensions which is been prepared through filling the gaps from review of Literature.

The above table shows that 90% of working women respondents shining with the traits as New Age women. 95% Respondents also agreed that they also hooked up by Self Image, Ready to break the stereotype, career and family oriented.

50% of the respondents are neutral for their enjoyment cum dedication towards job. This states that half of the respondents find it difficult to balance work and life. 90% of the respondents strongly disagree that they cannot separate work and life.

Conclusion

The research gives an idea to look forward about the Work-Life Integration. This is due to the acceptance of New Age Women in where their work and life are inseparable. They also accept that they think about job during personal time and personal priority during working hours or it has become clear that this attempt at a work-life balance is nearly impossible. Work-Life Integration approach which leads to synergies work and life, in which New Age Women need not to compromise any one. Work-Life Integration more appropriate and practical alternative for the striving and firm women worker who not only plays equal role on the success of both their job and personal life but seeks to knob both at the same time.

David Solomon, the global co-head of Goldman Sachs once said, “Today, technology means that we’re all available 24/7. And, because everyone demands instant gratification and instant connectivity, there are no boundaries, no breaks.” To ascertain a more practical connection to kinds of work arrangement employees often face today, the often used “work-life balance” is now being slowly chucked for “work-life integration” with blurring personal and professional limitations.

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